

Research Article

Discourse Analysis of Domestic Violence (DV) on Kompas Daily News (Sara Mills Model)

Lamri

Master Program, Faculty of Language, Arts and Culture, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia.
Email: lamri.2020@student.uny.ac.id

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Abstract: Domestic Violence (DV) often occurs everywhere so that this invites the attention of many media and often becomes the main news in the headline. Kompas Daily Media is one of the media that often highlights various cases, both cases that come from a number of homeland figures, celebrities and ordinary people. In many cases, men dominate domestic violence cases against women. This research focuses on the discourse of domestic violence in the media, 1) how the mass media displays the representation of women in the text, and 2) describes how the news text performs the strategy of appearing victims of domestic violence in media coverage. The research method used is a qualitative descriptive method using a critical discourse analytic approach to the news text entitled "*Detik-detik Suami Tendang dan Bacok Istrinya Saat Masak, Pelaku Ditangkap*" written in the Kompas digital newspaper on May 09, 2021, 14:36 WIB. The results showed that the author displays that Kompas.com has not made women a priority in the news text. Kompas.com news writers position women in the text as objects and there is a tendency for writers to place themselves in a male perspective. The news writer presents himself as a storytelling subject who represents the voice of the victim in the domestic violence case. Cultural codes are codes that can be used by readers to understand values, especially those related to the agreement of the readers.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis, Sara Mills Model, Domestic Violence.

Introduction

Women still dominate gender inequality compared to men, and have become one of the most discussed topics of discourse. Lull in Eriyanto explains that discourse is a way, idea or object that is openly debated to the public so that this results in a certain understanding that is very widespread (Sobur, 2018: 11). The discourse on women dominated by men appears a lot in the mass media, men make women as objects of sexuality, and attach the image of women as weak creatures, therefore in some print and digital media we still often encounter news about violence experienced by women.

Based on data from the National Commission on Violence against Women (Komnas Perempuan) reported during 2019, there were 431,471 cases of violence against women (VAW). VAW has increased by 792% in 12 years, which means that VAW in Indonesia has increased almost 18 times. Violence against girls (VAW) increased by 2,341 cases compared to 1,417 cases in the previous year. This increase increased by 65% and most cases were incest cases and added to cases of sexual violence (571 cases) (Komnas Perempuan, 2020). In addition, referring to data obtained from the Annual Record (Catahu) of the Indonesian National Commission on Women in 2017, sexual violence is violence that is often experienced by women in the household with a percentage of cases totaling 34% or 3,495 cases (Nisa, 2018: 59). Violence experienced by women, especially domestic violence, is a case that deserves attention from various groups considering that the impact that occurs is not only in the form of physical injuries to the female body but also has an impact on trauma and

psychological disorders. Furthermore, the media as one of the social institutions that report on domestic violence against women often makes most victims of domestic violence victims for the second time.

News that provides information on the issue of violence against women actually produces violence itself through the arrangement of sentences, labeling, and choice of diction so that the mass media in practice participates in preserving, strengthening, and even exacerbating gender inequality against women in society. Media coverage in presenting an idea or idea about patriarchal values and an understanding of the wrong gender perspective regularly and continuously ultimately forms the function of the media as an agent of gender socialization that perpetuates practices of gender injustice. Marshall McLuhan revealed that the media are extensions of man. The definition of man here is not in the sense of mankind (human) but leads to man as male-sex (male), so that the media in this case becomes a tool or instrument of male domination over women (Noviani, 2013). Gender inequality in mass media is not only reflected in advertisements or movies, but also in the news that continues to be constructed by the media.

The focus of attention in this research is the discourse of feminism, how women are presented in the text. Women tend to be presented in the text as weak, marginalized compared to men. This injustice and poor portrayal of women is the main target of this research. The same thing happens a lot in the news, many news articles feature women as the object of the news. News about domestic violence against women is one of the few news articles that feature women as the object of the news.

Theoretical Study

The definition of violence against women itself according to Article 1 of the Declaration on Violence against Women is: Any act based on sex differences that results in or may result in physical, sexual, psychological harm or suffering, including threats of certain actions, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether it occurs in public or in private life (Hasanah, 2013: 164). Next, Harkristuti Harkrisnowo reveals what is meant by violence against women, namely every form of violence directed against women simply because they are women (Muhajarah, 2016: 131). From the above definition, women become victims of violence because they have female sex, or it can be called gender-based violence.

Harkrisnowo then divides violence into various forms, namely: (a). Physical abuse such as hitting with hands or using weapons, kicking, stabbing, pushing, grabbing, spitting, slapping, and punching. (b). Emotional or psychological abuse, such as excessive possessiveness or jealousy, threatening suicide, isolating oneself from friends and social circles, damaging personal belongings, threatening the lives of others and partners or being able to hurt and mistreat people around or closest to them, manipulation and swearing, surveillance, hurting pets, intimidating to the point of fear, breaking promises, lying, and damaging relationships with parents, children, siblings and oneself. (c). Economic abuse is making a person economically dependent by controlling income and expenditure which is unreasonable and causes pressure on the partner. (d). Sexual abuse, which is an act of violence that coerces women to become prostitutes, forces them to have intercourse, mistreats them during intercourse, forces them to have intercourse after mistreating their partners, and uses animals or other rough objects during intercourse and so on (Muhajarah, 2016: 132). Sara Mills writes about discourse theory, especially discourse around feminism, therefore what Sara Mills proposes is called a feminist perspective. The point of attention of the feminist discourse perspective is to show how the text is biased in presenting women. The idea of Sara Mills (1992) is slightly different from the critical linguistic model as described in the previous section. Critical linguistics only focuses on the structure of language and how it affects the meaning of the audience. Sara Mills (in Eriyanto, 2011, p. 206) looks more at how the roles of actors are presented in the text and the roles of readers and writers are presented in the text. In the end, the style of exposure and the roles placed and displayed in this text will form legitimate and illegitimate parties, namely the ruling party and the controlled minority party.

The following is a framework with Sara Mills' analysis model:

Level	Things to See
Subject-Object Position	How events can be seen, from whose perspective they are seen. Who is positioned as the storyteller (subject) and who is the object being told. Does each actor and social group have the opportunity to present themselves, their ideas or their presence, their ideas are displayed by other groups/ people.
Author-Reader Position	How the reader is positioned and plays a role in the text. How the reader places himself in the text. To which group the reader belongs.

Methods

This research method uses the Critical paradigm. Furthermore, this research uses qualitative research. Creswell (2016) reveals that qualitative research is a type of research that explores and understands the meaning in a number of individuals or groups of people originating from social problems. Furthermore, this research also uses qualitative descriptive methods. Qualitative descriptive research is research that examines the content of a news text, both in the form of symbols and main ideas that exist in the theme of a news story (Badara, 2013: 63). The researcher then analyzed the news text using Sara Mills' critical discourse analysis. Sara Mills' critical discourse method emphasizes on how the positions of actors are displayed in the text. These positions are divided into the subject of the storytelling and who is the object of the storytelling which will determine how the structure of the text and how meaning is enacted in the text as a whole, In addition, Sara Mills also pays attention to how writers and readers are displayed in the text. The subject of this research is the Kompas.com online news portal, while the object of research is an online news article related to domestic violence entitled "Detik-detik Suami Tendang dan Bacok Istrinya Saat Masak, Pelaku Ditangkap" which was written in the Kompas digital newspaper on May 09, 2021, 14:36 WIB.

This study uses data sources consisting of two categories, namely primary data sources and secondary data sources. The primary data source in this study is the online media coverage entitled "Detik-detik Suami Tendang dan Bacok Istrinya Saat Masak, Pelaku Ditangkap" which was written in the Kompas digital newspaper on May 09, 2021, 14:36 WIB. Secondary data sources are obtained from literature in the form of books, documentation, and articles in the mass media, which are related to this paper. The data collection technique in this research is carried out by means of observation, namely by systematically observing and recording the phenomena being investigated or studied. The technique used next is to analyze the news using Sara Mills' approach along with other supporting literature that is still related to the theme of discussion in this study.

Results and Discussion

Detik-detik Suami Tendang dan Bacok Istrinya Saat Masak, Pelaku Ditangkap.

Kompas.com-09/05/2021, 14:36 WIB

Editor: Setyo Puji

KOMPAS.com-Kasus kekerasan dalam rumah tangga (KDRT) terjadi di Kabupaten Kupang, Nusa Tenggara Timur (NTT). Seorang istri berinisial NK (43), warga Kecamatan Amabi Oefeto Timur dianiaya suaminya sendiri berinisial YS (39). Peristiwa tersebut terjadi pada Kamis (6/5/2021) sekitar pukul 21.00 Wita. Saat kejadian itu, pelaku yang baru saja pulang pesta minuman keras dari rumah tetangganya kemudian mengamuk.

Pelaku langsung menendang korban yang saat itu sedang masak di dapur. Saat korban terjatuh, pelaku lalu mengambil parang dan membacok lutut kiri korban. Meski mengalami sejumlah luka, korban saat itu berhasil melarikan diri. Sehingga dapat terhindar dari amukan yang lebih parah dari pelaku.

"Korban berhasil melarikan diri sehingga tidak berlanjut pada tindakan kekerasan yang lebih fatal," ungkap Pejabat Humas Polres Kupang, Aiptu Lalu Randy Hidayat, Minggu (9/5/2021).

Korban yang merasa ketakutan dengan tindakan pelaku akhirnya memberanikan diri untuk melaporkannya kepada polisi. Setelah korban dilakukan visum dan dimintai keterangan, polisi langsung mengamankan pelaku di rumahnya tanpa perlawanan. "Kasus ini sedang ditangani Polsek Amabi Oefeto Timur. Para saksi dan korban serta pelaku sudah diperiksa polisi. Untuk penerapan pasal masih dalam didalami," ujar dia.

Penulis: Kontributor Kupang, Sigiranus Marutho Bere

Sara Mills' discourse analysis in the reporting of news texts emphasizes how women are portrayed in the text. Sara Mills (in Eriyanto, 2011, p. 200) using Althusser's analysis prioritizes the role of actors in the text. This role is said to be a form of positioning a person, namely as an interpreter and an interpreted position. Emphasizes how actors are positioned in the text. Therefore, there are two things that must be prioritized, namely how the actors in the text are positioned and how the actors as interpreters or interpreted in the news. The role of the actors in the text both as interpreters and interpreted is to interpret the occurrence of events like what and how. It will even have an impact on how the reader's role in the text is the result of negotiations between the reader and the author. This is an illustration that the reader is described by the author according to the author's imagination.

Level	Things to See
Subject-Object Position	<p>Discourse with the issue of domestic violence in the news title <i>Seconds Husband Kicks and Slashes His Wife While Cooking, Perpetrator Arrested</i>. 09/05/2021. The title selection defines women as objects whose job is to serve and provide dishes for their husbands, the article of her drunk husband is not highlighted in the title, only briefly mentioned by the author, here is the quote <i>“sekitar pukul 21.00 Wita. Saat kejadian itu, pelaku yang baru saja pulang pesta minuman keras dari rumah tetangganya kemudian mengamuk”</i>. Women as victims of domestic violence are positioned as objects where details about domestic violence events, how the process and occurrence of domestic violence, are not known from the victim but from the perspective of others. There is no woman's voice in the news text, so the domestic violence event in the news marginalizes the position of the victim. The victim is not given the opportunity to speak for herself, she is not present and her presence is brought up in the text through the perspective of others. The following is the quotation <i>“Pelaku langsung menendang korban yang saat itu sedang masak di dapur. Saat korban terjatuh, pelaku lalu mengambil parang dan membacok lutut kiri korban”</i>. The text tells how easy it is to trick victims, the author through this news does not present the involvement of women to speak directly. The news makes women (victims) as objects so that they do not provide opportunities for women to tell about themselves as sources. This news text is told from a male perspective, complete with prejudices. Furthermore, women are not only not featured, but their presence is represented by others and positioned as the party who is partly responsible for the perpetrator's guilt. The author presents himself as a subject who represents the voice of the victim in the domestic violence case, the news is trying to be conveyed like the victim's confession</p>

	conveyed through the police for the events that happened to her.
Author-Reader Position	<p>According to Sara Mills (in Eriyanto, 2011, p. 202) news is not merely a product of media crews/journalists and readers are not placed solely as targets, because news is the result of an agreement between the wishes of journalists and their readers. Therefore, therefore, in studying the context, it is necessary to pay attention to other contexts from the reader's side as a comparison text. Thus, it is not enough to only pay attention to the context written by a journalist in understanding a context.</p> <p>In the discourse, the text is conveyed indirectly through the cultural code method. This term was introduced by Ronald Barthes to refer to the cultural codes or values used by the reader. The writer's position here is as a storyteller, because there is no direct expression from the victim (woman/ wife of the perpetrator). When interpreting a text, such as by using the sentence <i>Para saksi dan korban serta pelaku sudah diperiksa polisi</i> It suggests a certain amount of information that is believed and recognized as a shared truth. Cultural codes are codes that can be used by readers to understand values, especially those related to those that are in agreement with their readers.</p>

The explanation of the research results above shows that Kompas.com news writers position women in the text still as objects. Women have not been able to present themselves or tell the events that happened to them so that the truth presented by the media is not told from the woman's side. Furthermore, based on the analysis conducted on the Kompas.com online news portal media, it shows that Kompas.com media has not made women a priority in the news text. Kompas.com through its news still places women as objects and the tendency of writers to place themselves in a male perspective.

Conclusion

The results showed that Kompas.com has not prioritized women in the news text. Kompas.com news writers position women in the news text as objects. Women have not been able to present themselves or tell the events that happened to them so that the truth presented by the media is not told from the woman's side and there is a tendency for writers to put themselves in a male perspective. The news writer presents himself as a storytelling subject who represents the voice of the victim in the domestic violence case. Cultural codes are codes that can be used by readers to understand values, especially those related to those that have an agreement with their readers.

Declarations

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